

Study On The Internal Cause Regression Of Juvenile Musical Instrument Selection In Baoshan City, Yunnan Province Under The Perspective Of Quality Education

Xiao-Li Yang, Jia Li

Article Info

Article History

Received:
March 18, 2023

Accepted:
June 20, 2023

Keywords :

Quality Education,
Baoshan City, Yunnan
Province, Adolescents,
Musical Instrument
Selection

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.8056888

Abstract

With the continuous reform of art education in primary and secondary schools, instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools has also developed to a certain extent. Instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools has been the weak link in students' art education and has been underappreciated for a long time, which has seriously hindered the development of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools and affected the improvement of students' quality education ability. The purpose of this study was to determine whether there is a relationship between music student-specific personality traits and timbre preferences for instrumental music selection in social music quality education at the secondary school level (including middle and high school).

Introduction

Music has the function of expressing emotion and cultivating sentiment. The goal of music education is to develop students' quality from a cognitive and aesthetic perspective through this art form. Currently, in order to respond to the call of the historical mission to achieve the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, it has also become one of the important contents of quality education in music education to expose students to more traditional and ethnic music, to cultivate their national spirit and patriotism, and to promote the development of music in China (Cai Zhaomei, 2006).

The current situation of music education in primary and secondary schools presents the following major characteristics:

(i) Strong interest

The survey found that among many courses, students have a strong interest in music lessons. Moreover, they are able to take the initiative and actively participate in the course. This is conducive to the development of students' active learning and active expression of character. This is also one of the goals of quality education (Jiang Youbiao, 2006).

(ii) Obvious character

Primary and secondary school students are at a stage where they are more receptive to new things and influenced by popular elements. Students clearly show a preference for popular music in their music learning. Therefore, it becomes a very important issue to realize the goal of combining students' interests with quality education in teaching (Qin, Hongbo, 2007).

In addition, in daily life, students are also easily influenced by some folk music, which inevitably contains some vulgar elements. Therefore, we also need to improve students' judgment and appreciation of music (Li, Ying, 2019).

(iii) Students' individual developmental characteristics

As we all know, students' feelings about music do not only come from classroom education. In their daily lives and extracurricular activities, students are also exposed to other forms of music. Students have distinct personalities and different types of music they like, and in the classroom, uniform teaching materials may not always meet the needs of students. Especially as they get older, middle school students are more unconstrained by the music provided by the materials in the classroom. Therefore, it is also important for teachers to recognize this change in their teaching and design content and methods that are appealing to students and can better achieve their teaching goals (Zhang, 2014).

(iv) Teachers' awareness has increased

Many teachers in the teaching force already have a certain understanding and awareness of quality education. This awareness is also consciously put into teaching in the specific classroom. Schools have also provided special music teachers or equipment, etc., for music teaching. However, there are still inevitably incomprehensive and unsystematic problems in teaching. This can affect the penetration of quality education in music teaching (Zheng, Ke-Jiao, 2009).

Combining music education and quality education in primary and secondary schools

First of all, to realize the infiltration of quality education in music teaching, we must start from the fundamental purpose of quality education. Combined with the above analysis of the characteristics of current music education, we can see that teachers should provide students with diverse and attractive teaching contents, develop students' musical abilities, such as singing and playing musical instruments, and are students have a full understanding of the beauty of music to achieve the goal of students' active learning and feeling of music (Xu Hongshuai, 2007).

Music class has been considered as an entertainment and pastime course in people's conception, and its function in school education is to cultivate sentiment, cultivate the spirit of collectivism, and carry out moral education as an auxiliary means, in addition to improving students' aesthetic ability, how to play music aesthetic ability, which is commonly referred to as the function of aesthetic education. How to play the unique role of music education in improving the quality of students is an important issue facing the current music teaching reform (Han Hong, 2013).

I. Understanding of quality education in music teaching

In music disciplines, both music composition, appreciation, performance and criticism have their own research fields and have a complete theoretical system, which is a completely independent discipline. No matter which of these disciplines the learner engages in, the learner needs to understand, imagine, associate, remember, and create. The involvement of multiple thinking functions explains that music learning has the same characteristics of mental work as other intellectual disciplines, i.e., it has intellectual characteristics. Unfortunately, people are accustomed to teaching music by singing and playing musical works, and viewing music education as a whole without thinking, let alone creativity (Fan Hongling, 2014). This is inevitably a biased generalization. Learning singing and playing skills and techniques in music classes, like basic skills in other applied disciplines, is only a basic means of study and application, not the whole content and purpose of music education. It is well known that music education, as an important part of aesthetic education in schools, can play an important role in the development of students' moral, cultural, scientific, psychological and physical qualities. However, under the conditions of exam-oriented education, not only the proper status of music education is neglected by many schools, parents and students to varying degrees, but also the above-mentioned functions of music education are seriously affected. With the current deepening of quality education and the establishment and implementation of the concept of quality education, the foundation has been laid for establishing the proper status of music education, which also provides a good opportunity for the reform and development of music teaching (Hu Ling, 2014).

Second, the role of quality education in music teaching

Under the general environment of quality education, the position of music education will be gradually improved and the function of music education will be better played. Music education can promote the development of students' intelligence. Many famous people with high intelligence in ancient and modern times and in China, such as Confucius, Einstein, Rousseau, Goethe, Lenin and so on, mostly love music, and it can be said that music has a certain influence on their career achievements. Music education in school not only helps students to understand the objective world figuratively and expand their intellectual horizons, but also promotes intelligence with music, so that their intelligence can be developed in many ways. For example, in music appreciation and singing, students will produce a series of mental activities such as attention, memory and imagination, which can promote the development of students' attention, memory and imagination, and let them acquire active thinking ability; in instrumental music performance, students use their hands, brains, eyes and ears, which can greatly develop their intelligence, comprehensively develop their intelligence, exercise their creative ability, and make them become creative talents with comprehensive development (Tian Guangming, 2012). However, due to the long-term influence of exam-oriented education, music teaching often has the stigma of exam-oriented education to varying degrees, and there are still directions in music teaching that are detached from quality education. For example, in music teaching, there is also the problem of using the vision and requirements of professional education to look at music education in ordinary schools: pay attention to the quality of a music open class, ignoring the quality of teaching in general; pay attention to the training of top music talents, ignoring the education for all students; pay attention to music professional knowledge, skills training, ignoring the important auxiliary promotion role of music education for moral, intellectual and physical education. Even in some "backbone" teachers who do teaching public classes and demonstration classes, there is a problem of catching a few "key" music classes. These practices are contrary to the quality of education. Although there have been various experiments on music teaching reform under the conditions of test-taking, and certain results have been achieved, it should be said that only under the general environment of quality education is the direction of music teaching reform really given and the conditions for the success of the reform created (Wen Xiaowu, 2011).

The implementation of quality education in music teaching

School music education should pay attention to grasp the basic characteristics of music, let students fully enjoy all the beauty of music, use the beauty of music to cultivate temperament, establish a healthy aesthetic interest, and realize the change from examination-based education to quality education. In the practice of music teaching, we should insist on facing all students, respecting students, and promoting the development of students' subjective consciousness, that is, human independence, creativity and subjective initiative, so that everyone can succeed (Chen Fang, 2011). For example, in the instrumental music teaching of the harmonica in the classroom, attention is paid to the inner potential of students, but the individual differences of students must be faced. Since the mouth organ is a group teaching instrument, it is relatively easy to learn, but it also requires students to master the skill of blowing using breath control, and to master the correct fingering of the right hand. In order to make students all have the space to fully express themselves and learn through their own personal experience and initiative. Unintentionally develop students' playing ability, feeling ability, performance ability and cooperation ability. Thus, it plays a role in promoting the formation of healthy psychological quality of children. For example, in the choral teaching of the lesson "The Valley is Quiet", the connotation of the beautiful scenery of nature in the textbook was explored, and a learning environment was created for students to feel the mood expressed in this art song: the podium of the music classroom was covered with flowers and green grass. Using modern e-learning media, a huge picture of the forest was projected (Li, 2011). The lighting is arranged with some shades of green colored strips to make the classroom moderately and softly lit, and the blackboard is hung with large, neat, clear song pieces that are very eye-catching. When the music starts, a video clip depicting the scenery of nature cut from the TV movie "Animal World" is then played. The image of this art song has static and dynamic, and then the dynamic strengthens continuously, and the intensity fades to the weakest after the climax. In this perfect combination of sound and image, the children's emotions were touched by this teaching atmosphere. They were as if they were in the scene, and developed rich imagination and association. They felt the beauty of the famous mountains and rivers of the great motherland. Together with the teacher's vivid teaching language, accurate and beautiful command gestures, and smooth and expressive piano accompaniment, it undoubtedly played a subtle inculcation and infection to the students (Zhang Ting, 2011).

In conclusion, quality education in music teaching not only promotes the development of students' attention, memory, and imagination, and allows them to acquire active thinking ability: it also causes great changes in their disposition, spirit, temperament, as well as their ideology, way of thinking and even their way of life, allowing them to acquire healthy psychology and good behavioral habits throughout their lives, greatly developing their intelligence, exercising their creative ability, and making them become creative talents with all-round development (Qilin Li, 2011).

Social Music Education

Social music education is a perspective of aesthetic education, which is an "amateur discipline" derived from sociology, education and musicology, and is a social music education activity composed of art groups and industry associations. Because the organizing unit is the cultural and artistic enterprise sector, social music education is often neglected by the education sector, leading to its cultivation mode to "artisanal", "fast food", "follow-the-wave""homogeneity" and "utilitarianism". Although this model has played a certain role in popularizing the "music knowledge" of the examination group, the Ministry of Education proposed in 2020 to strengthen the cultivation of "core literacy" in youth aesthetic education, which proves that social music education has received high attention from the national policy level. However, the Ministry of Education's proposal in 2020 to strengthen the "core literacy" of youth aesthetic education proves that social music education has been given high priority at the national policy level, and it is of practical significance to re-examine the responsibilities and obligations of social music education (Xu, 2007).

The piano examinations of social music education were first introduced in 1987 by the Shanghai Conservatory of Music and the Guangzhou Baoshan Piano Society, and have become a "scenery" of social music education since then. The Central Conservatory of Music, the Chinese Musicians Association, and the Shanghai Conservatory of Music are all three music institutions that conduct social music education activities within their respective administrative areas. In 1990, the Chinese Musicians' Association, the Chinese Conservatory of Music, the Chinese Opera and Dance Theatre, and the Chinese National Orchestral Society also conducted music examinations nationwide. "According to statistics, there are 48 social music examination institutions nationwide approved by the Ministry of Culture, including 6 national social music examination institutions and 42 local social music examination institutions." b The number of examination groups has exceeded one million. c However, with the approval of examination institutions and the increase of examination types, there has been a greater generalization of examination standards and alienation of examination perceptions. d This paper takes piano examination education research as an example and uses the unique perspective of social music education fulfilling its responsibility to explore what kind of social responsibility social music education should actually fulfill (Gu, 2014).

Path analysis of the formation of examination level alienation education

The essence of art education is the education of aesthetics and literacy, and over the past 40 years of reform and opening up, the model of art examinations has regarded it as education that "seeks to survive", and this "seeking to survive" is precisely along the "utilitarianization This "survival" is based on the "utilitarian" concept of technical education, which is used in exchange for the "technical expression of the examination certificate". First, the cultural infiltration and export of Western countries. "According to relevant statistics, the current cultural output of Yunnan Province accounts for 42.6% of the world's total cultural market, ranking first in the world, the cultural industry of Yunnan Province accounts for 25% of the national GDP, has exceeded aviation, agriculture, especially the film and television culture of Yunnan Province, music and art culture, with its mass, entertainment most directly affect our country. " e Secondly, from the perspective of sociological outreach, there are three types of purposes of learning piano examinations: the first type is to let the child take a professional route, pouring the family's efforts to cultivate "skilled", after reaching a certain level to benefit from the identity of special students in the future of higher education examinations, also known as "craft artisan type "The second category is not caring about the result at the moment, let the child learn a specialty, learn some music knowledge for urgent use, called "emergency fast food"; the third category is climbing to follow the trend, other children are learning, their own children can not lose in the starting line, called The third type is to follow the trend, other children are learning, their own children can not lose the starting line, called "follow the trend". In comparison, these three types of education are homogeneous and "utilitarian". Third, the individual examiner is trying to get a "certificate" in social education. In my years as an examiner, social piano examiners in many regions are approaching a misconception of "external practice", i.e. sculpting and chiseling every note (Wang Feng, 2013).

At a time when core literacy and cultural confidence are being comprehensively promoted, we have gradually clarified the responsibility of social music education and its cultural fulfillment, and social music education has subtly influenced sociology and pedagogy from the single technical mode of examination to the comprehensive development mode of "core literacy". From the small family to the large social classroom, the audience of social music education has moved from micro to macro. Piano education has undergone a qualitative change, from the technical to the cultural level, which has caused a debate in the industry, and is an extension of music technology to core literacy from the perspective of the music discipline. The scale of development of social music education and the function of music and culture education have drawn great attention from all walks of life, and its penetration into national culture is invisible and has become a subject of in-depth study in the academia (Deng Tingzhi, 2013).

Motivation of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine whether there is a relationship between music students' specific personality traits and timbre preferences in the selection of social quality education instrumental music at the secondary school level (including middle and high school). Secondary research objectives were related to student instrument selection, matching students to their timbral preferences, and to specific instrument and timbral gender stereotypes (Cui, Lina, 2011).

Participants (N = 624) were social music education students from four school districts in Baoshan City, Yunnan Province, and many participated in relevant social examinations. Data were collected using three testing instruments: the Baoshan Education Bureau Sample Statistics Questionnaire produced a descriptive profile of participants, the Baoshan Education Bureau Youth Personal Style Questionnaire provided results for five personality traits (agreeableness, self-awareness, emotional stability, extraversion, and openness), and the Baoshan College Institute of Social Music Instrument Timbre Preference Test collected timbre preference data. Multiple linear regression analyses revealed that participants' levels of extroversion and openness personality traits were significantly correlated with timbre A (flute), B (clarinet), C (saxophone and horn), E (trumpet), F (trombone, alto, and horn), and G (tuba) ($p < .05$). In addition, the analysis showed that gender stereotypes were observed in both instrument choice and timbre preference. In secondary instrumental music, gender was a significant predictor of timbre choices A, B, F, and G. The majority of students did not use the same instrument as their timbre preference. In addition, most students did not play on instruments consistent with their timbre preferences; however, the percentage of beginners using instruments consistent with their timbre preferences was 26.3% and approximately 53% for high school students (Z. Ma, 2011).

Significant relationships were found between personality traits, timbre preference, gender, and instrument choice among middle school instrumental music students. Levels of extraversion and openness, as well as gender and instrument choice, were found to be significant predictors of timbre preference. Knowledge of these relationships may be useful for secondary school social instrumental music instruction in helping undecided beginning instrumental music students choose their first instrument (Zhao, Mengxin, 2010).

Theoretical foundation

This study is based on Alpert's trait theory (personality classification theory). Personality, which has been defined as a general term for individual thoughts, emotions, behaviors, and attitudes, is a branch of psychology; however, personality disorders, formerly known as personality abnormalities, have been monopolized by

psychiatry. In psychology, personality has been analyzed in five dimensions: Neuroticism, Extroversion, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, and Openness (Guo Ge, 2014).

According to Zhao Jing, the term "character" is somewhat ambiguous because it implies people's moral judgment of someone. For example, when we say that someone has a "good character", this moral judgment is included. Alpert prefers to "define character as character that is evaluated and character as character that is not evaluated. Alpert first developed the trait theory of character. Alpert divided traits into common traits and individual traits (Zhao, Jing, 2019).

Common traits are the same traits that are shared by most people or a group in a certain socio-cultural form. When studying cultural differences in personality, it is possible to compare common traits in different cultures. Individual traits are those traits that are unique to an individual. Personal traits are divided into primary, central, and secondary traits. Primary traits are the most typical and generalized traits of a person; central traits are several important traits that make up the uniqueness of an individual, and there are about 5 to 10 central traits in each person; secondary traits are some less important traits of an individual, which are not expressed in general. Often, they only manifest in special situations (Zhao, Jing, 2019).

The Yunnan Provincial Psychiatric Association, also in its Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Personality (1994), lists personality disorders as delusional (Paranoid), schizoid (Schizoid), schizotypal (Schizotypal), acting out (Histrionic), narcissistic (Narcissistic), antisocial (Antisocial) Borderline, Avoidant, Dependent, and Obsessive-compulsive (Chen, Lei, 2014).

Analyzing the aspects that make up personality, Alpert breaks down personality into four components: attitudinal traits, volitional traits, emotional traits, and rational traits (Jiang, 2014).

Attitudinal traits of personality mainly refer to the personality traits of how a person deals with all aspects of society, i.e., the personality traits of his attitudes toward society, toward the collective, toward work, toward labor, toward others, and toward himself. The attitude characteristics of character, the good performance is loyal to the motherland, love the collective, care for others, helpful, selfless, upright, sincere, civilized and polite, hardworking and frugal, serious and responsible, modest and cautious, etc.; the bad performance is no national temperament, indifferent to the collective and others, selfish and self-interested, detrimental to others, treacherous and cunning, brutal and rude, lazy and profligate, perfunctory, irresponsible, arrogant and arrogant etc. (Ding Jing, 2013).

The volitional characteristic of personality refers to the characteristic of a person who regulates his or her behavior consciously. According to the quality of the will, good will is characterized by ambitious ideals, planned actions, independence and independence from others; decisiveness, courage, perseverance, perseverance and self-control; bad will is characterized by being blind, blind, following the crowd, easily suggestible, indecisive, self-indulgent or stubborn, cowardly, capricious, etc. (He Aijun, 2012).

Emotional traits of personality refer to the influence of a person's emotions on his or her activities and his or her ability to control his or her emotions. Good emotional characteristics are good at controlling their emotions, stable emotions, and often in a positive and optimistic state of mind; bad emotional characteristics are easy to cause emotional reactions to everything, and emotions have a greater impact on the body, work and life, and the ability of the will to control emotions is weak, emotional fluctuations, and the state of mind is easy to be negative and pessimistic (Chen JF, 2010).

Rational characteristics of personality refer to a person's personality characteristics in cognitive activities. For example, independence and dependence in cognitive activities: those who are independent can actively observe according to their own tasks and interests and are good at independent thinking; those who are dependent are easily disturbed by irrelevant factors and are willing to borrow ready-made answers; 'realism in imagination: some people have a strong sense of reality while others are rich in fantasy; precision in thinking activities: some people can think deeply and look at problems comprehensively; some people are lack of initiative and have a strong sense of reality. Some people have a strong sense of reality, while others are fanciful; the accuracy of thinking activities: some people are thoughtful and comprehensive, while others lack opinions, follow the clouds or take the bull by the horns, etc. (Lu, 2010).

Personality

Personality is a stable attitude towards reality and the habitual behavior that corresponds to this attitude. Once formed, personality is relatively stable, but not unchanging, but malleable. Character is different from temperament and reflects more the social attributes of character, and the core of the difference between individuals is the difference of character (Song Ping, 2010).

Personality is a stable attitude toward reality and the character traits expressed in the habitualized behavior corresponding to this attitude (Jiang Yu, 2011).

Attitude

Attitude is a disposition to react to people, objects, or ideas that is acquired in later life and consists of three factors: cognitive, affective, and behavioral tendencies. A person's attitude toward reality is expressed in what

he pursues and rejects in life, i.e., in what he does above all. And how a person does it indicates how he behaves. A person's stable attitude toward reality determines his way of behavior, and the habituated way of behavior reflects his attitude toward reality (Qi Yalin, 2011).

Attitude determines the way of behavior, and a stable attitude makes the way of behavior that is compatible with this attitude, which slowly becomes habitual and naturally manifests itself. It is a characteristic of a person's character to help people, and he will not hesitate to help others when they are in trouble. Others will see his helpful behavior will also feel very natural, very consistent with his character traits. A selfish person, if others see him to help people, but feel very strange and incomprehensible. Therefore, a person's attitude toward reality, which is developed in a long social life, and his way of behavior are closely related and inseparable (Tian, 2011).

Character is formed gradually in the practice of social life, and once it is formed, it is more stable, and it will be expressed at different times and in different places. However, the stability of character does not mean that it is unchanging, but it is moldable. After personality is formed in a person's life, major changes in life environment will definitely bring about significant changes in his personality traits (Song, Ping, 2010).

The results of this study showed a significant relationship between gender and tone preference. These findings provide a new perspective on an old question. Compared to the large literature on gender stereotypes in instrument selection, there are few studies on gender and timbre preference (Wisong Wu, 2005). The present study may reveal a new dimension to gender stereotypes, that is, the relationship between gender and timbre preference. Because timbre preference was measured without the use of real instrument sounds, the important results of this study may contradict the current literature that contains research. If secondary school social instrumental music instruction chooses to use information from the current study, matching students to their timbre preferences may allow the phenomenon of gender stereotypes to occur, but placing students on their respective instruments while considering gender and timbre preferences would be most beneficial to the students and the program, as retention rates may increase based on the Song-Ping premise.

In the present study, timbre preference was found to be significantly associated with openness and extraversion personality traits. ($p < .05$), supporting the results of previous research (Wu, Weisong, 2005). The majority of participants in this study (64.9%) therefore observed actions in this study that contradict Yang's premise about matching students' timbre preferences to the instruments they play. The proportion of participants who matched their timbre preferences gradually increased from 1 in 4 beginners (26.3% on average) to more than 1 in 2 high school students (53.9%). The results showed a significant relationship between gender and instrument choice ($p < .001$), supporting the current published research (Wisong Wu, 2005). However, a significant relationship was also found between gender and timbre preference ($p < .001$), which may contradict the current literature on gender stereotyping in secondary instrumental music. Results indicated that gender also selected timbre A, B, E, F, and G as a significant predictor ($p < .05$), with R^2 , ranging from .010 to .102. Once loaded into the regression model, six significant regression equations were found ($p < .05$), finding that timbre A (flute), B (clarinet), C (saxophone and horn), E (trumpet), F (trombone, alto, and horn) and G (tuba), and gender, instrument choice, openness, and extraversion were shown to be significant predictors of timbre preference.

Conclusion

Three areas are recommended for inclusion in further research: increasing ethnic diversity, improving measurement precision and testing timbre preference, and conducting in-depth research on timbre choice between openness, extraversion, and gender loadings as they relate to music instrument classification. The first recommendation centers on conducting the study with a more diverse ethnic sample in order to achieve a stronger level of generalization beyond the current sample range. Although the sample was identified with consideration of district enrollment records obtained from the Institute in Pausan, the search for participating school district purpose in both rural and urban schools inadvertently skewed the sample diversity. However, the sample was statistically consistent with the selection of the participant population (school district) sample.

While the current sample is representative of the sample from which it was drawn, the results are difficult to generalize beyond a limited number of districts. Replicating this study with a more diverse sample would provide greater external validity and strengthen the significance of the findings.

Although the Ebin Tone Bias Test is the only test of its kind, the reliability and validity of this test has been questioned by some researchers using synthetic and actual tones. Further development of a new test using actual instrument sounds while controlling for instrument identification and subsequent comparison with the results of this study would allow for additional analysis of personality traits, timbre preferences, gender, and instrument selection relationships.

The research literature suggests that woodwind players are more conservative than brass or string players (Waisong Wu, 2005). The results of this study showed that there was a significant difference between openness and extraversion loadings in the regression model measuring timbre preference of instrument families. In

addition, there were similar differences in gender loading in the same regression equation. In-depth examination of these instrumental family differences may provide insightful information about the attributes that contribute to such differences (Waisong Wu, 2005).

In summary, researchers investigating timbre preferences for instrument selection of students for secondary instrumental music should continue to examine the relationship between timbre preferences and personality traits, including openness and extraversion. Directors should examine other important predictors of timbral preference gender and instrument choice. Further research on these variables may be integral to secondary school social instrumental music instruction in many areas such as instrument selection of students, ensuring ensemble balance, increasing as well as improving instrumental music efficiency.

Maintaining enrollment and increasing student satisfaction. The results of this study suggest that the use of personality questionnaires and timbre preference tests may improve the accuracy of secondary school social instrumental music instruction in recommending instruments to undecided prospective students, which in turn may improve instrumental music retention across secondary schools. The relationship between timbre preference and gender should also be examined in greater depth for researchers and secondary school social instrumental music instruction, as the significant relationships revealed in this study may alter perceptions of gender stereotypes. Thus, the relationship between personality traits and timbre preference, as well as the study of openness, extraversion, gender, and important predictors of instrument choice, remains a viable and indispensable area of additional research (Wisong Wu, 2005).

References

- Wu, Shan. (2022). Innovation of instrumental music learning styles in elementary schools from a life field perspective. *New Curriculum Studies* (21), 96-98.
- Chen Yan. (2021). A study of instrumental music teaching permeated with metacognitive cultivation. *Art View*(31),109-110.
- Cao Lei. (2020). Beautiful because of perseverance: A study on the implementation of instrumental music learning in high school music class. *New Course*(46),83.
- Fang Yuxi. (2022). The Importance of Ethnic Instrumental Music Learning in Quality Music Education in Primary and Secondary Schools. *Folk Music*(01),118-121.
- Yi Bin. (2018). A survey study on the current situation of instrumental music teaching in secondary schools in Shanghai (Master's thesis, Shanghai Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201802&filename=1018028285.nh>
- Na Ritai. (2015). Exploring the current situation and development of instrumental music teaching in elementary school (Master's thesis, Inner Mongolia Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201601&filename=1015432528.nh>
- Guo Ge. (2014). A study on the influence of external and internal motivation on instrumental music practice behavior (Master's thesis, Huazhong Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201402&filename=1014235318>.
- Zhao Jing. (2019). Instrumental music teaching energizes students' music learning. *New Education*(23),49-50.
- Xu Wei. (2018). Strategies of instrumental music learning for students in provincial compulsory education. *New Curriculum Review* (12), 84-95.
- Chen Lei. (2014). The role of psychological quality in instrumental music learning. *Science and Technology Information* (23), 234. doi:10.16661/j.cnki.1672-3791.2014.23.181.
- Jiang, S.L.. (2014). Making instrumental learning a lubricant for music lessons. *Curriculum Education Research* (06), 229.
- Ding Jing. (2013). An introduction to the use of encouraging evaluation in the primary teaching stage of musical instruments. *Gansu Science and Technology*(09),9 3-94+30.
- He Aijun. (2012). The current situation and countermeasures of children's amateur instrumental music development. *Journal of Lanzhou Jiaotong University* (05), 182-184.
- Chen JF. (2010). Talking about the cultivation of inner listening in instrumental music learning. *Popular Literature and Arts* (02), 190.
- Lv Zhenxia. (2010). Motivation for instrumental music learning in various forms. *Campus Psychology* (01), 67-68.
- Song, Ping. (2010). The development of students' self-regulated learning ability in instrumental music teaching. *Literature and Education* (22), 120-121.
- Jiang Yu. (2011). How to cultivate students' interest and habits in learning instrumental music. *Big Stage*(12),244+76.
- Qi Yalin. (2011). Promoting the development of students' physical coordination through instrumental music learning. *Popular Literature and Arts* (20), 212.
- Tian Wenge. (2011). The role of instrumental music learning in improving students' quality. *Henan Education (Late)* (Z1), 86. doi:10.16586/j.cnki.41-1033/g4.2011.z1.018.

- Song, P.. (2010). Psychological differences in students' learning styles and teaching strategies in instrumental music teaching. *Teachers*(23),98.
- Yang Yan. (2010). The similarities and differences between adults and children in instrumental music learning. *Art Education*(09),109.
- Wu Weisong. (2005). Developing intellectual factors from instrumental music learning. *Music World* (08), 7-8.
- Cai Zhaomei. (2006). The effect of instrumental learning on children's non-intellectual factors. *Music World* (04), 24-25.
- Jiang Youbiao. (2006). A study on the value of instrumental learning. *Artistic exploration* (S1), 90-92.
- Qin Hongbo. (2007). An introduction to instrumental music learning and examinations. *Science and Technology Information (Science Education and Research)*(13), 166.
- Li Ying. (2019). How to strengthen the fun of instrumental music teaching in the music classroom of primary and secondary schools. *New Curriculum (Next)*(10),99.
- Zhang Liang. (2014). A study on the current situation of instrumental music teaching and teaching improvement in primary and secondary schools (Master's thesis, Hebei Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201501&filename=1015541540.nh>
- Zheng Kejiao. (2009). Exploring the problems that constrain the development of instrumental music in primary and secondary schools. *Examination Weekly* (03), 91-92.
- Xu Hongshuai. (2007). Research on the development of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary school music education in China (Doctoral dissertation, Capital Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CDFD9908&filename=2007076415.nh>
- Han Hong. (2013). A brief discussion on instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools in the new era of curriculum concept. *Music World*(01),10-1
- Zhao Mengxin. (2010). Exploration and research of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools (Master's thesis, Hunan Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD2012&filename=10110700> [1] Wang Feng. (2013). Research on instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary music education (Master's thesis, Hebei Normal University). <https://kns.cnki.net/KCMS/detail/detail.aspx?dbname=CMFD201401&filename=1014160600.nh82.nh>
- Fan Hongling.2014(07). Factors affecting the development of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools and improvement strategies [J]. *Popular Literature and Arts*
- Hu Ling.2014(06). Analysis of factors affecting the development of instrumental music in basic music education [J]. *Music Time and Space*
- Tian Guangming. 2012(01). Research on the teaching of instrumental music in primary and secondary schools in Shaoxing City--practice and research on instrumental music teaching in the context of new standards [J]. *Journal of Shaoxing College of Arts and Sciences (Educational Teaching Research)*
- Wen Xiaowu. 2011(07). Let instrumental music teaching move [J]. *New Course (Comprehensive Edition)*.
- Chen F. 2011(06). The embodiment of quality education in primary and secondary music education [J]. *Music World*.
- Li Haitao. 2011(01). A preliminary study on the effectiveness of multimedia application in junior high school music teaching [J]. *Modern education science (secondary school teachers)*
- Zhang Ting. 2011(01). The impact of "network potential music education" on music education in primary and secondary schools [J]. *Journal of Weinan Normal College*
- Li Qilin. 2011(01). Stimulating students' interest and cultivating collective harmony: Experiences in teaching instrumental music in secondary schools [J]. *New Course (Next)* [39] Chen Yunfeng. 2009(09). Let the sound of the piano ride on the wings of music--Talking about how to get out of the dilemma of classroom instrumental music teaching[J]. *Chinese Music Education*
- Xu Hongshuai. 2007. Study on the development of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary school music education in China [D]. Capital Normal University
- Gu Tianliang. 2014. Analysis of the current situation of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary school classrooms and research on countermeasures [D]. Shenyang Normal University
- Wang F. 2013. Research on instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary school music education [D]. Hebei Normal University
- Liu Wanlu. 2013. Research on the theory and practice of effective instrumental music teaching [D]. Capital Normal University
- Deng Tingzhi. 2013. Study on the current situation of instrumental music teaching in Changsha elementary school and countermeasures [D]. Hunan Normal University
- Cui Lina. 2011. Survey and analysis on the current situation of elementary school students learning western wind music [D]. Northeast Normal University
- Ma ZQ. 2011. Study on the effectiveness of instrumental music teaching in junior high school classroom [D]. Shanghai Normal University

- Zhao Mengxin. 2010. Exploration and research of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools [D]. Hunan Normal University
- Sun Bingbing. 2010. Study on the history and current situation of instrumental music teaching in primary and secondary schools in Yantai [D]. Qufu Normal University
- Jia Ligeng. 2003. The Current Situation of Instrumental Music Teaching in Dalian Out-of-School Education and Reflections on Art Education [D]. Liaoning Normal University

Author Information

Xiao-Li Yang

International College, Krirk University, Thailand

Jia LiInternational College, Krirk University, Thailand
